

14th April 2022

TO WHOMSOEVER IT MAY CONCERN

This is to certify that **Nijith M** from **College of Hotel Management and Tourism – Srinivas University** has completed his Industrial Training in core four departments (Front Office, Housekeeping, Food & Beverage Service and Culinary) from **13th December 2021 – 13th April 2022**.

During his training his overall performance was good.

We wish him success in all his future endeavours.

For Fairfield by Marriott Bengaluru Rajajinagar,
(A Unit of Samhi Hotels Pvt. Ltd.,)

Himanchli

Himanchli

Human Resources Manager

